

A Guide to Delivering Operationally Sustainable Research Infrastructure: An Australian Perspective

Sachintha Jayasinghe^{1,2,3}

¹ Chief Executive Officer, Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation, St Lucia, Queensland, Australia

² Adjunct Professor (Research Infrastructure), The University of Queensland, St Lucia, Queensland, Australia

³ Associate (Research Infrastructure), Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, Australia

Abstract

Research infrastructure, encompassing people, equipment, specialised space and digital assets, are a key enabler of research discovery and societal impact. Coordinated research infrastructure provides institutions with the means to effectively and efficiently deliver capabilities to internal end users and engage partners across industry and government. However, there are multiple elements to consider in provisioning operationally sustainable research infrastructure within the context of a finite resources in the Australian research and innovation eco-system. This paper outlines these elements and provides best practice advice for the Australian research community.

Keywords

Research Infrastructure; Platform Technologies; Core Facilities; Research Facilities; Shared Resources

Introduction

Research infrastructure is a key enabler in realising research excellence and impact, often being a vital cog in the academia-industry-government partnerships of the innovation eco-system. As such, universities and other research organisations must position their research infrastructure within the broader strategy and operations of the whole institution. Broadly, institutions need to ensure the researcher infrastructure program is optimally configured to maximally leverage and develop new opportunities aligned with the organisation's research strengths; and look to continuously improve efficiency (and productivity) within the finite resources available.

Research infrastructure entails deep expertise (people), equipment, specialised spaces (e.g., clean rooms) and digital assets (e.g., health data sets). Research infrastructure capabilities enable research across the spectrum of fundamental discovery to novel innovation. It plays a critical role in:

- Delivering research project outcomes;
- Attracting new research talent to the institution;
- Leveraging research and commercial opportunities with industry;
- Developing new methods and tools; and
- Training the next generation of researchers on the latest technological advancements.

Coordinated research infrastructure is often referred to as ‘core facilities’ or ‘platform technologies’; each facility/platform operating as a business or budget unit within the host organisation. Not all research infrastructure needs to be hosted under a core facility – this is a considered decision based on several factors. Research organisations will have a deliberate strategy for research infrastructure management and investment. Without a strategy and planning (and policy and coordination), institutions risk inefficiencies and ultimately ineffective delivery of research infrastructure capabilities. This is not only about building one’s own capabilities but also brokering the right partnerships to ensure access to cutting-edge research infrastructure in other organisations. The formulation and delivery of such strategy requires dedicated leadership and supporting governance structures. Many of the research-intensive Australian universities have a Pro Vice-Chancellor (Research Infrastructure) or equivalent position, albeit this is a relatively new initiative within the sector.

Invariably, research infrastructure is cross-subsidised by teaching and/or other revenue streams of a university or a medical research institute. Typically, a university is called to invest (off-the-top) up to 70% of the operating and capital costs associated with delivering the said capabilities. Within the limited public funding of the national research eco-system, prudent oversight of core facilities is essential, including periodic review and benchmarking. A key element of such benchmarking is financial performance and operational sustainability.

The two major dedicated research infrastructure funding schemes are the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (~\$500M per annum) and the Australian Research Council’s Linkage, Infrastructure, Equipment and Facilities. The latter is predominately for equipment with its mere circa \$39M per annum pool not having significantly increased for the last decade. There are many other opportunities in the Australian funding eco-system to attract funds in support of research infrastructure. However, such support is often restricted to the capital and equipment components and not for the specialist expertise and ongoing operations and maintenance (as opposed to research fellows and/or research assistants).

Key considerations for provisioning operationally sustainable research infrastructure

Establishing core research facilities

Not all research infrastructure has to be placed within a core facility. Those capabilities that tick one or more key attributes can be considered for consolidation, namely:

- The end-users of the research infrastructure represent multiple disciplines; in a university context this entails cross-faculty and/or cross-departmental use;
- The technologies are complex and require expert staff to facilitate optimisation of experiments and training of Higher Degree Researchers;
- Demand for the research infrastructure will endure beyond one or two research groups;
- There are substantive fixed costs associated with operating and maintaining the capabilities; and
- The operating scale will be in excess of \$500,000AUD per annum (at the time of this publication).

Consolidation of research infrastructure capabilities can be achieved through the following broad categories (thus provides practical scale for establishing independent operating business units):

- Analytical and Characterisation;
- Omics, with close links to bioinformatics;
- Bioresources (animal, glass houses);
- Design and Fabrication; and
- Data Science and eResearch (including digital humanities and social science data platforms).

Operating models

Prior to considering sustainable delivery of research infrastructure, the home institution must adopt a clear and consistent operating model. There are three broad operating models for delivering coordinated research infrastructure. The model adopted will reflect the overall operating principles and structures of the home university/institute and the scale of research activity.

Model 1: Centralised

- In consultation with stakeholders, develop strategy and deliver operations to end-users via a central research infrastructure unit/office. In a university context, such a unit often sits within the portfolio of the Deputy Vice-Chancellor (Research) or equivalent.

Model 2: Matrix

- In consultation with stakeholders, develop strategy and policy and manage research infrastructure investments within a central research infrastructure unit/office. Individual divisions (with option to delegate to institutes, schools and/or centres) host research infrastructure capabilities on behalf of the organisation and facility operations provided by divisional administration.

Model 3: Devolved

- In consultation with stakeholders, develop broad strategy and policy within Office of the Deputy Vice-Chancellor (Research) or equivalent. Individual divisions (with option to delegate to institutes, schools and/or centres) host research infrastructure capabilities on behalf of the organisations and facility operations provided by divisional administration. Divisional Executive set direction and make investment decisions.

Operating model and research scale

For Australian universities, research scale can be associated with the Higher Education Research Data Collection (HERDC) research ‘income’. Those institutions with an annual HERDC return between \$20-\$150M are best served by adopting a centralised model. At this scale, it is feasible for a central research infrastructure unit to effectively engage with the research community and fully leverage the economies of scale to maximise efficiencies (and avoid duplication of effort). Once the scale is beyond \$150M, the degree of activity and nuances of individual academic disciplines, will present challenges for a central office to effectively engage with the research community, often leading to delayed and poor decision making. Thus, the matrix operating model is ideal for balancing day-to-day decision-making at the local level, but with active management of broader research infrastructure decisions from the central office. A good example is the central office running equipment replacement schemes where applications are formulated at the faculty-level taking into consideration discipline-based priorities. For smaller universities with modest

research income, the investment in a centralised research office is unlikely to provide sufficient dividends, either in terms of enhanced effectiveness nor efficiencies. In contrast, the sheer scale of HERDC income of \$600M plus will pose challenges under even a matrix model. If indeed a matrix model is adopted, the central office will likely only focus on very high-level decisions and broad policy. As a reflection of scale, it is not unusual to duplicate research infrastructure capabilities when at these higher scales. This is often based on demand by end-users (i.e., research scale) and/or highly specialised application and customisation of platform technologies to meet discipline-based needs. Such specialisation is often seen in biomedical versus materials science microscopy applications, for example. Figure 1 notes a summary representation.

Figure 1: Optimum Research Infrastructure Operating Model for Research Scales (based on HERDC)

The biggest folly made by institutions is to adopt mixed operating models concurrently within the same organisation. Mixed models will generate unhealthy internal competition; yield poor end-user experience; and result in missed opportunities with external stakeholders and prospective clients due to ineffective coordination within the home organisation.

Roles and responsibilities under operating models

	Centralised	Matrix	Devolved
Research Infrastructure Executive	Ensure strategic alignment with strategic plans; develop and implement policy; ensure efficient operations within funding/operating models; direct/influence strategic investments; lead external engagement	Develop strategy and policy in alignment university-wide strategy and plans; deploy strategic investments; monitor performance and ROI; lead external engagement; influence operations, mentor Facility leaders	No dedicated RI Executive; broad strategy and policy from research executive; monitors performance and ROI
Central Research Infrastructure Support	Management accounting; web/collateral content coordination; metrics collection and reporting; benchmarking; continuous improvement projects; space management; governance support; leads engagement with corporate services	Web/collateral content coordination; allocation of strategic investments based on guidelines/priorities; governance support; supports engagement with corporate services	No dedicated central RI support; broad policy development and communication; facilitating engagement with corporate services

Faculties/Institutes/ Schools/Centres	Feedback to RI Executive; participate in governance; contribute to End- users/Advisory Groups	Based on central policy, responsible for hosting and managing select Facilities on behalf of researchers; report on performance metrics; collaborate with RI Executive to deliver effective and efficient research infrastructure capabilities; contribute to End-users/Advisory Groups	Based on broad central policy, responsible for hosting and managing facilities on behalf of researchers; provide dedicated research infrastructure leadership/management; report on performance metrics; contribute to End- users/Advisory Groups
End-users/Advisory Groups	Inform future investment and direction to drive innovation within existing platforms and/or develop new capabilities	Inform future investment and direction to drive innovation within existing platforms and/or develop new capabilities	Inform future investment and direction to drive innovation within existing platforms and/or develop new capabilities
Research Infrastructure Capabilities/Facilities	Manage capabilities and day-to-day local operations; reports to RI Executive	Manage capabilities and day-to-day local operations; reports to Faculty/Institute Executive with 'dotted line' to central RI Executive	Manage capabilities and day-to-day local operations; reports to Faculty/Institute Executive
External Partners	Engages the institution via RI Executive on strategic and substantive operational matters	Engages the institution via RI Executive on strategic and major co-investment matters	Engages institution via host Faculty/Institute Executive

The research infrastructure workforce

The sector oversimplifies the research infrastructure workforce with the predominate use of the term 'technical' and unintentionally devaluing the contribution of research infrastructure expertise, which spans both Academic and Professional staff tracks. The legacy of technical staff, including staff involved in preparation of teaching and learning laboratories, means that there remain some existing biases within the sector; negatively impacting reward and recognition of the research infrastructure specialists. This workforce includes scientists, engineers and other specialists who contribute direct intellectual input in the innovation-ecosystem.

Successful research infrastructure provisioning is dependent on highly talented and dedicated people. At the cold face of research infrastructure, one must identify three broad cohorts: 1) Technicians; 2) Academic Contributors; and 3) Specialists. Using the Queensland University of Technology (QUT) as an example, characteristics of the three cohorts are outlined in Table 1. Typically, a university embeds technical services first¹, followed by Academic Contributors², and finally investment in Specialists³ coinciding with significant research scale and complexity of research infrastructure capabilities. Formal management of research infrastructure business units (i.e., Managers and Directors of Core Facilities) can come from any of the three cohort types.

Table 1: Exemplar Research Infrastructure Workforce Profile of QUT

Broad Position Title(s)	HR Track(s) & Range	Characteristic(s)	Examples
Technicians ¹	HEW 4-8	Generic support, often managing bespoke research infrastructure spaces and oversee related maintenance; overlap with teaching laboratory and technical services	-Senior Technician (Mechanical Operations) -Senior Technician (Workshop Operations)
Research Officers/Fellows (Academic Contributors) ²	Levels B-E	Have discipline focus with application of one or more research infrastructure capabilities underpinning the research effort (part-time work allocation to research infrastructure)	-Senior Research Officer (Surface Science) -Principal Research Fellow (Elements & Isotopes)
Research Infrastructure Specialists/Core Scientists ³	Levels B-E	Deep technology platform capability applied to a breadth of research disciplines	-Research Infrastructure Specialist (Synchrotron Science) -Research Infrastructure Specialist (Surface Mass Spectrometry)
Research Engineers ³	HEW 8-9/ Levels B-E	Application of engineering capabilities	-Senior Electrochemical Engineer -Principal Research Engineer (Mechanical)
Software Developers ³	HEW 6-10	Developing and adoption of data collectors and analysis tools and delivering advanced visualisation platforms	-Software Developer (Dynamic Collections) - Lead Software Developer (Web & Integrated Systems)
Technologists ³	HEW 6-9	Akin to Research Infrastructure Specialist but do not (yet) possess the national/international standing within applicable community of practice	-Analytical Chemistry Technologist (Laser Ablation ICP-MS & XRF) -Senior Technologist (Biorefining)

Academic Contributors are often early and mid-career researchers. Though their immediate colleagues and supervisors will acknowledge their contributions to acquiring, maintaining, advancing, training and experimental design as related to research infrastructure, often the formal recognition during academic promotion is lacking. The traditional metrics for academic performance leaves little room for nuancing.

Whilst acknowledging the complexities of the enterprise bargaining agreements, institutions should use the staff tracks, that is Academic and Professional, as a tool to enable recruitment and retention of talent. There are two key considerations:

- 1) Modify the institutional research and/or academic career frameworks to explicitly recognise research infrastructure talent, which in turn opens the path for promotion

underpinned by relevant performance metrics and standards. This is especially pivotal for Academic Contributors and Research Infrastructure Specialists/Core Scientists; and

- 2) In the Australian university context, only the Academic track recognises the person. In order, to compete within the market for high calibre talent, it is not sufficient to rely on the Professional track (about the job, not person) with its limitations. This is highly relevant to recruitment and retention of software developers and engineers, for example. Therefore, institutions should look to accommodate the use of the Academic track as a human resource tool, with a clear view that these incumbents are highly unlikely to be or become ‘academics’ and adopt the traditional titles that accompany each level of the Academic track. Rather than Level E Professor, consider Level E Principal Engineer, for example.

Recruiting, retaining and developing research infrastructure talent

The single most important consideration for delivering operationally sustainable research infrastructure is investment in talent. The recruitment, retention and development of the expertise is pivotal to fully leveraging platform technologies and enduring effective contributions to research and innovation. However, the Australian higher education sector is still grappling with dichotomy of the Academic and Professional tracks of current enterprise bargaining agreements, and how best to nurture the research infrastructure workforce.

Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow’s model, in its simplest version, is a 5-tier pyramid for motivation (Figure 2, Maslow, 1943). Lower levels need to be satisfied (not necessarily 100%) in order progress, and can be applied to organisations and employees. It can also be dynamic – consider the impact of a formal organisation-wide restructures prompted by financial pressures. The proceeding uses the Maslow’s model in the context of the research infrastructure talent (it is assumed that physiological needs are already satisfied).

Figure 2: A Simplified Representation of Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs

Safety

It is not possible to effectively nurture talent when incumbents are anxious about ongoing job security. Whilst there is business sense in some short-term contracts (12-months or less), it is often the default position for appointing research Infrastructure staff. Frequently there is no appreciation of opportunity costs and an unsophisticated approach to assessing the risk profile in decision making. There is legitimate rationale for exercising caution appointing ongoing roles. Organisations must be equitable in approach across divergent pace of technology advancement (e.g., genomics vs electron microscopy). Moreover, when institutions secure first one-in-the state- or country-technology platforms, international recruitment is often necessary, thus longer-term contracts becomes essential. As one invests in people for the longer-term, ensure allocation of funds for professional development as part of business as usual.

Sense of Connection

Within academia, it is well understood the role of mentoring and coaching Higher Degree Researchers and early/mid-career researchers, often solely through the lens of an academic discipline. It is not unusual for the research infrastructure workforce to be relegated to the background, especially as they often represent multiple disciplines through divergent research applications. As such, institutional executive needs to play a proactive role in clarifying:

- Where do I fit?
- How do I contribute?
- How will my contributions be recognised?
- What are my objectives?

Establishing a sense of connection is especially challenging within the Australian higher education dichotomy of Professional (about job) and Academic (about person) staff tracks. As scientists contributing to original intellectual outputs, the research infrastructure staff on the Professional track have to be treated as talent, not job positions. Organisational executive must proactively and regularly foster a clear line-of-site between the research infrastructure workforce and the institution's strategic goals – revisits are often required as priorities can change dramatically as was the case with the Pandemic. A sense of connection can be achieved by links to primary research activity (e.g., membership in centres and participation in grants); co-authorships and research outputs (by for example, embedding school-based academic staff in core facilities); explicit recognition of the research infrastructure cohort in the formal academic career frameworks; overtly acknowledging unique expertise (e.g., in job titles, published staff profiles); and promotion of staff achievements and contributions in impact stories.

One cautions against exclusive reliance on business development units to leverage research-industry opportunities. Ultimately, investment in developing the research infrastructure workforce so that they may themselves lead the industry engagement, participate in project co-design, and facilitate risk-informed decision-making will provide substantial dividends for a research institution. Foremost, this professional development entails the nurturing of an entrepreneurial mindset. Recognition of further opportunities within day-to-day transactional services will lead to productive partnerships with industry, government, and external academia. This in turn will reaffirm a sense of connection to the overall vision and mission of the organisation.

Esteem

Status is a core component of academia for reward and recognition and peer-review. Thus, esteem for the research infrastructure workforce must harmonise with the organisational and sectorial cultural norms, otherwise one risks marginalising and demotivating this relatively small, but critical cohort of staff. This can be as simple as highlighting the contribution of research infrastructure experts (as individuals) in research outputs and acknowledge the role the incumbents play in training the next generation of researchers (example, in Figure 3). Moreover, provide

'Secrets of Earth's largest carbon sink revealed by synchrotron research'

The research team, led by Dr Christoph Schrank from QUT's School of Earth and Atmospheric Sciences, Dr Michael Jones from QUT's Central Analytical Research Facility, and Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO) synchrotron scientist Dr Cameron Kewish, published their findings in the Nature journal Communications Earth and Environment.

Queensland University of Technology, 2021

specific job titles that explicitly capture the expertise of the staff. Often, research organisations adopt the generic 'technician' for titles.

Self-actualisation (the Best One Can Be)

Not all staff desire promotion and career advancement. However, organisations must provide equitable pathways for those seeking such advancement. Ultimately, the home organisation needs to provide the setting for the staff to be the 'best one can be'. By adopting the broad concepts of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, institutions can nurture a high performing cohort of research infrastructure talent.

Figure 3: Demonstration of Esteem in acknowledgment of Research Infrastructure Talent in Contributing to Research Outputs

Research Infrastructure Leadership & Governance

Research intensive Australian universities have dedicated senior roles (typically at the level of Pro Vice-Chancellor) to oversee research infrastructure portfolios, regardless of the operating model adopted. This role reports to the Deputy Vice-Chancellor (Research) or equivalent. Not only do such roles look to align research infrastructure provisioning with research (and teaching and learning) strategy of the institution, but also play a critical role in influencing enterprise/corporate functions. Moreover, they build partnerships with industry and other institutions, looking to leverage opportunities where available, supporting the university research community towards impactful research outcomes.

The aforementioned dedicated senior research infrastructure leadership needs to be complemented with sound governance structures, which includes membership focussed on divergent expertise as opposed to internal divisional (e.g., faculty-based) representation. Typical layers of governance include:

- A group that provides the institutional executive with high level advice as it pertains to whole-of-organisation investment in research infrastructure. This group is about academic/research investment decisions; thus, membership should reflect this mandate. Under delegated authority, this group will scrutinise bids and make funding recommendations across operations and capital; play a key role in monitoring emerging national and state opportunities; and ensure policies and procedures have the sufficient

agility and flexibility to respond to new prospects. Over time, such governance builds on experience, growing to be a source of ‘wisdom’ that the home institution will rely on in making good investment decisions (often decisions will need to be made under short notice with limited information);

- A group that focusses on major research infrastructure projects, both planning and delivery (i.e., does not make academic investment decisions). This could entail major procurement activity or capital space refurbishments, for example. Project planning and delivery goes beyond an academic endeavour, and internal partnerships with corporate services and expertise is paramount for successful delivery of major research infrastructure initiatives. Therefore, membership of this group should be representative of broad expertise; and
- A facility-specific end-user advisory groups will inform priorities, speak to research infrastructure capability alignment to research (and in turn support application to grant schemes such as Australian Research Council’s Linkage, Infrastructure, Equipment and Facilities), and provide immediate feedback on operational matters.

The dedicated senior leadership, supported by fit-for-purpose governance, will ensure integrated planning and project delivery, with agility built-in to deal with the unexpected, whether a threat or an opportunity. This is especially critical for long-term planning considerations such as estates master planning across university campuses.

The research infrastructure workforce must work hand-in-hand with organisational corporate services. Of particular criticality is areas of procurement; estates; health, safety and environment, and information technologies. Whether its importation of highly advanced equipment or designing fit-for-purpose clean rooms, success is dependent on a collaborative approach to delivering research infrastructure.

Research Infrastructure Systems & Processes

The ability to successfully query the financial performance and end-user demographics of research infrastructure utilisation can be extremely difficult. Core facilities booking systems can address the latter issue and be a key tool for communicating with end-users. In adopting a consistent operating model, institutions must harmonise research infrastructure business units (i.e., individual core facilities), reflected in the ‘general ledger’ structures within enterprise financial systems. It is imperative such structures facilitate ready-reporting of agreed financial performance and monitoring indicators.

It is important that a balanced approach is taken in measuring the performance of coordinated research facilities – financial performance is only one element. The objective is enabling research and impact; thus, the obvious starting point is the task of capturing facility contributions to research outputs and its role in solving industry problems. Financial reporting needs to be overlaid with the said contributions as reportable key performance indicators.

In consideration of both internal researcher and external industry clients, an institution needs to implement a quality control and assurance program. Such a program should leverage best practice standards such as ISO9000 Quality Management Systems without necessarily taking on the full burden of certification. Practically, quality control programs take into account instrument performance such as laser alignment, measurement against standards, and so on. Ultimately, the quality program needs to publish the data regularly (i.e., intranet) towards building trust of end-users.

As an endeavour for continuous improvement, an annual survey needs to be deployed. The proactive solicitation of formal feedback creates transparency, accountability and identifies areas for ongoing improvement. Part of the transparency is calling out ‘outliers’, which can on occasion represent a single incident (positive or negative) that does not represent the broader performance standard of a research infrastructure facility.

Collectively, policies and procedures and the list of research infrastructure capabilities need to be consolidated for the benefit current and prospective end-users. Effective mechanisms for sharing information are paramount, this includes a dedicated intranet as well as a single externally facing website.

Whilst systems are not the panacea, they can enhance communication (and not rely exclusively on on-one-on relationships) and provide transparency (and in turn accountability) to end-users and institutional research infrastructure staff and leadership.

Coordinated Research Infrastructure (aka Core Facility) Finances

Market-driven Pricing

The prices (i.e., schedule of end-user fees) set up by core facilities should reflect prevailing, comparable market rates for the services rendered. Moreover, the prices need to acknowledge the end-user status (i.e., tiered pricing to reflect internal researchers, external researchers, industry partners, institute affiliates, etc), consistent with institutional policy and competitive neutrality legislation (i.e., public funds not adversely impacting private sector providers). A pricing strategy driven exclusively by cost-recovery targets is ineffective, as the market will govern price positioning. The operational cost is core facility dependent, noting that many asset-rich and complex technologies have significant fixed-cost burdens of equipment maintenance service contracts and salaries for specialised scientific staff. Noting the high proportion of fixed costs, a cost saving strategy is unlikely to yield material dividends, especially if the total operational scale is relatively modest (less than \$5M per annum). Similarly, it is ineffective strategy to simply reduce prices under market rates in an attempt to draw end-users. Ultimately the success of the core facilities is reflected in the research enabled. As such, any underutilisation of research infrastructure capability needs to first look to invest in parallel efforts in stimulating research projects, thus proactive engagement with potential end-users during major grant funding rounds by core facility scientists is paramount as well as developing opportunities with industry.

Pricing and Special Subsidies

Price benchmarking of like-for-like core facilities can often encounter situations where there is significant subsidy for ‘internal’ end-users, well beyond the level of institutional investment for a particular research infrastructure capability. For example, University One will fund 50% of the operating cost in running its bioresource facilities through a ‘central’ investment. However, the Department X may in turn further subsidise the prices for its researchers by an additional 20%, thus the internal price for the departmental researchers is significantly less. Here, the Head of Department is making a strategic investment decision within his/her delegated authority.

Pricing Labour

In addition to ‘how much’, often core facilities can be challenged by ‘what’ and ‘when’ to charge in terms of core facility staff labour. Whilst there is an expectation that some education, training and guidance is to be provided by research infrastructure specialists, one must be attentive when

core facilities staff make significant contributions to experimental design and direct research project assistance. Such contributions must be acknowledged via formal recognition (e.g., co-authorship) and labour cost-recovery – these are not mutually exclusive. Not only is this important for operational sustainability of the core facilities, it also ensures fairness across the end-users by provision of equitable access to core facilities scientists and technical expertise.

Pricing and Grants

Noting the dependency on funded research, it is important to acknowledge the typical grant cycle of 3 years. As such any changes to core facility pricing must provide sufficient forewarning so that researchers can budget accordingly into outyears. Therefore, a communication campaign would flag price increases in early 2023 ahead of major grant rounds, indicating that the new prices will come into effect in 2024. As not to adversely impact current research grants, there needs to be also provision for a grace period where a procedure is outlined so that impacted end-users can make a case for continuing with the ‘older’ prices.

Variable Operating Ratios

The cost recovery targets need to be tailored for each core facility. It is certainly not appropriate to compare core facilities within a single institution, but rather look to national peer facilities to benchmark. For example, the ratio between institutional investment and cost recovery may be 80:20 for preclinical-imaging capabilities whilst the inverse for flow cytometry. In addition to associated fixed costs, there are many other variables that govern this operating ratio, including:

- Some technologies are ubiquitous to certain research fields (e.g., flow cytometry in immunology and cancer) and often can operate 24/7; and
- Institutions can invest in new technologies that are cutting-edge, but will not have a large end-user base, nonetheless yield ground-breaking research (e.g., human 7 Tesla MRI).

In recognition of such divergence, it is vital institutional executive manage core facility financial performance (expectations) accordingly. A cost-recovery target should be set, but one that is appropriately benchmarked to other peer facilities. Otherwise, one risks demotivating the responsible managers and core facility staff with unachievable objectives, and thus distracting them from efforts in actually sustaining and delivering successful research infrastructure capabilities.

As a ratio target (i.e., percentage of operating budget), it is important to note that overall costs can increase with core facility growth. Therefore, institutional executives will always have to assess and critique future investments in core facilities – do the benefits outlined outweigh the future costs of this new research infrastructure capability?

A Mixed Cost-recovery Model

One of the challenges of core facility cost-recovery models is forecasting portfolio revenue returns in management accounting and reporting – the income lines can be rather ‘bumpy’. Many core facilities across the country adopt subscription-based fees in granting access to end-users. The motivation is unlikely to be consideration of financial forecasting, but rather simplifying access. However, it does capture some revenue upfront, helping to alleviate cash flow anxieties of institutional executives. As such an organisation may consider introducing a mixed model of subscription and fee-for-service (per hour, per sample, etc) for its core facilities. The subscription may be in the form of a ‘registration fee’, which will also ensure commitment from end-users that participate in training and induction (these are typically in the range of \$200-500 per end-user).

Operational Sustainability and Performance

If not cost saving, how does one improve operational sustainability? Firstly, it is important that a balanced approach is taken in measuring the performance of core research facilities – financial performance is only one element. The objective is enabling research and impact; thus, the obvious starting point is the task of capturing core facility contributions to research outputs and its role in solving industry problems. Financial reporting needs to be overlaid with the said contributions as reportable key performance indicators, withstanding the challenge of obtaining the required data from institutional enterprise systems.

Since core facility costs are predominately fixed, revenue generation is key to achieving operational sustainability and growth. An entrepreneurial mind-set is vital to developing new and further leveraging existing partnerships. Therefore, core facilities need to proactively engage in nurturing opportunities, collaborating with business development and engagement functions of the institution (as well as directly engaging with key researchers and industry clients). Another critical and often difficult decision for institutions is divesting quickly from underutilised capabilities, for example, by on-selling ‘lazy’ assets. One can still maintain research infrastructure capabilities without necessarily directly hosting the equipment. This can be achieved by investing in core scientists and embedding them in partner organisations, but very much have the remit of incumbents focussed on serving the end-users of home institution, for example. Another underutilised strategy is garnering support for operations (i.e., salary) as part of partner co-investment during major equipment schemes, rather than exclusively for the capital costs (and therefore acknowledging the total cost of ownership).

Managing Assets

Those core facilities underpinned by sophisticated instrumentation are bound to proprietary vendor servicing and maintenance. Post-warranty vendor service and maintenance contracts can be a shock to core facility budgets, but very much an unavoidable fixed cost. Therefore, it is critical that each core facility work with the research community to develop capability roadmaps, where part of the consideration should be staggered replacement of ‘workhorse’ instrumentation. Across a research infrastructure portfolio, institutions need to avoid major asset cliffs within single year (which in turn can present an operating budget challenge if all instruments come-off warranty simultaneously).

Promotion, Communication & Engagement

It is not unusual for researchers within a home institution not being fully aware of the spectrum of core facilities and research infrastructure capabilities available to them. The cycle of attrition and onboarding of new staff and students call for proactive promotion of core facilities through use of effective communication channels and engagement modalities. The tactics and approaches utilised are highly dependent on the operating model adopted by the home research organisation. The previously noted roles and responsibilities under the different operating models will dictate where the remit for communication and maintenance of the promotional assets, such as the website presence, sits within an organisation. For example, under the centralised model of provisioning research infrastructure, the central research infrastructure support office will have primary responsibility for determining when, how and what to communicate to stakeholders.

Reinforced with policy and procedures, institutional executive must reiterate the value of research infrastructure capabilities and highlight the investment (i.e., the subsidy). Without ongoing communication and engagement with the research community, the prevailing sentiments can be exclusively of ‘the cost to my research’ when using core facilities. Often, the research community is not even aware of the institutional subsidy in research infrastructure operations and the potential to capture this investment as ‘institutional support’ during research grant applications. This manner of strategic communication and engagement is distinct from marketing collateral and the web presence. In this case, it is much more nuanced, addressing elements of organisational culture and how end-users view core facilities.

Often publicly funded research organisations do not go beyond research infrastructure websites and printed marketing collateral in terms of external engagement, especially as it pertains to industry. As noted earlier, research infrastructure talent themselves can nurture productive partnerships with industry. A centralised website can aid discoverability. However, it has often proven to be the least effective engagement tool. Industry sectors are diverse and the modes of engagement are also complex. As such, the promotion has to be targeted and the communicated content needs to include more than technical specifications such as project management expertise and the position on intellectual property.

A key element to sustainable operations of research infrastructure is actual uptake of core facility capabilities. Discoverability and ready access to core facility services is critical. It is highly recommended that:

- Organisations include details of core facilities as part of new staff and student induction processes, especially aligning with graduate schools and intake of Higher Degree Researchers;
- Deliberately adopt business systems (e.g., instrument bookings software platforms) that facilitate ready communication with end-users – current and future;
- Contribute to institutional internal and external communications (e.g., newsletters from the office of a Deputy Vice-Chancellor (Research));
- Host dedicated research infrastructure/core facility events, combining end-user case studies and showcase of platform capabilities;
- Host a single, institutional website and intranet for information, even under devolved operating model and hosting of core facilities is distributed across, for example, several university faculties; and
- Participate in regional and national research infrastructure forums for information sharing and coordinating optimised approaches to leveraging opportunities (e.g., the Queensland Major Research Infrastructure Alliance).

Declaration of Interest Statement

None.

References

Maslow, A. H. (1943). "A theory of human motivation". *Psychological Review*. 50 (4): 370–396. doi:10.1037/h0054346.